

Diversities and similarities of the vowel system in English for intermediate students in Uzbekistan

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Annotation: This paper deals with the relative study of vowel and consonant organized whole of English and Uzbek languages. Focused on the articulation of the in good condition of both languages, points to the characteristic in sounds articulation and acoustics, talk over the nearly commonplace mistakes make by the Uzbek learners in the speech pattern of the English vowels and consonants.

Key words: vowels, consonants, similarities, a sound, comparative analysis, pronunciation, English language.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена сравнительному изучению гласных и согласных, организованных в целом в английском и узбекском языках. Акцентируется внимание на артикуляции в хорошем состоянии обоих языков, указывает на характерные особенности в артикуляции звуков и акустике, обсуждает почти банальные ошибки, допускаемые узбекскими учащимися в структуре речи английских гласных и согласных.

Ключевые слова: гласные, согласные, сходство, звук, сравнительный анализ, произношение, английский язык.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida tashkil etilgan unlilar va

undoshlarni qiyosiy o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Ikkala tilning yaxshi holatidagi artikulyatsiyaga e'tibor qaratiladi, tovushlar va akustikaning artikulyatsiyasidagi xarakterli xususiyatlarga ishora qiladi, ingliz unlilari va undoshlarining nutq tuzilishida o'zbek o'quvchilari tomonidan yo'l qo'yilgan deyarli ahamiyatsiz xatolarni muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: unlilar, undoshlar, o'xshashliklar, tovush, qiyosiy tahlil, talaffuz, ingliz tili.

The require to learn foreign languages, in particular English, more and more require scientific search of the principal typological characteristic of the phonetic, lexical, grammatical process of systems of foreign and native languages. In this affection recently, lingules generally refer to distinguished point of view of the relative analysis of various languages. The relative study of phonetics, in our opinion, is one of the relevant and nigh important difficulty of modern linguistics. Due to the truth that each studying foreign terminology sets a destination to professional a foreign language and practice it in practice, the role of pronunciation increasingly increases. Undoubtedly, the discover of a foreign language is accompanied, fundamental of all, the study of phonetics and, in addition, wrong decorated articulation construct it difficult, and sometimes violates the understanding and communication between the speakers.

The defective possession of pronunciation skills may be the cause of numerous errors and incorrect interpretation of words of words, which will serve as a semantic problem when communicating. Thus, to understand a foreign language speech and correctly express your thoughts on someone else's language, you need to have certain knowledge of the phonetic system, main phonetic phenomena and the laws of this language. It is also necessary to remember that all the lexical and grammatical phenomena of the language materialize in its sound sheath English and Uzbek

languages compare are languages related to various language groups and types. Uzbek language is the language of the Turkic group, agglutinative type. J. Buranov gives the following definition of this type of languages: "Agglutinative languages - languages characterized by the morphological sign of which is the implementation of word formation and word by imposing the unambiguous affixes having a strict sequence" [1]. It is indisputable that the discover of English in the Uzbek interview cannot flow separated from the peculiarities of the phonetic development of the Uzbek language.

The study of polysynthetic Uzbek and flexive English languages is in reality a study of calculation languages, which construct it possible to recognize distinctive and general categories in compatible languages, to distinguish voice difficulties associated with the assimilation of the uttermost average of the non-standard language and the causes of violation of the orthoepic standards. A particular feature of the articulation of English vowels is the speech pattern of vowels [I:], [I], [E], with a flat ruffle, patch Uzbek [i], [E] are well-defined with the neutral situation of the lips, not exposing the teeth.

In Uzbek vocalism, 3 cuddered sounds are presented: [u], [o '], [o] and as many non-bred vowels: [i], [a], [e]. In English, 4 cubed monophthong is represented: [ɔ:], [ɔ], [u], [u:] and 3 difthong kernels: [ɔI], [ʊ], [ʊə]. All other vowels belong to non-screw sounds. Uzbek labialized vowels are distinguished by a large rounding and repulsion of the lips, while in English rounding is insignificant. In English, there are different continuance and standard of long and short couple of vowels:] - [I], [ɔ:] - [ɔ], [u] - [u:], [ʌ] - [ɑ :] And having a pair of instrument [E] [æ]. What is more this phenomenon is of a phondematic character: replacement in the duration of the vowel necessitate for themselves and change in the sense of the word, for example: Torn - [T ɔ: N] Ton - [T ɔ N], Beat [BI: T] - Bit / Bit /, Pool / Pu: L / - Pull / Pul /. The typological signs of the British national subsystem and the lack of these

characteristic in the transaction of vocalism of the Uzbek language lead to numerous mistake in the pronunciation of English words. In Uzbek, for example, the consequence of the harmony of vowels entails the distortion of English words consisting of indefinite syllables. The harmony of vowels is to practice vowels of one row as a result of the consequence of the first vowel to the next. Errors allowed when pronunciation of English vowels are harder to prevent or prerogative than errors in the articulation of consonant sounds. This is explained by the fact that the various attitude of the language during the pronunciation of vowels harder to experience or see.

In addition to the above differences, which accommodate the qualitative characteristics of English and Uzbek vowels, thither is a differentiation based on quantitative features, which make clear all other differences such as intense - weak, severe-weak. Uzbek vowels are, as a rule, "medium" sounds out plumb nor long nor short. In Uzbek language, the limitation of the word is determined by the deaf consonant, which is essentially contradicts English spoken skills, since in English at the end of the word is well-defined a strong voice consonant. A characteristic of the Uzbek communication is the law of harmony of vowels inherent in all Turkic languages, on the basis of which the vowels are harmonized and along the palating line and on the line of labiality. The essence of the compatibility of a series is that if the fundamental vowel root is a vowel reverse, so vowel invest in rows (and vice versa) are used in the added word-formative and word effects), for for instance do'mboq (full) + Qina (decreased affix) = do'mboqqina (full), nozik (gentle) + kina = nozikkina (gentle) (affixing of a diminution and lascalng number).

English language is unusual for sygarmonic phenomena of type harmony of vowels. Here in one word can be combined with vowels and front and rear rows and labialized and non-bias. For example: Funny (funny) - ['Fʌni], BECAUSE (because) - [bi'kəʊz].

Thus, by us, the comparative analysis of the audio systems of English and Uzbek languages allows us to identify the typological features of the consonantism and vocalism of both languages, to establish identical and distinct features in the sound system of the languages compared. In the article, we tried to point out some difficulties that may arise from Uzbek students when studying and mastering the audio system of English.

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